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Exploring the Effect of Price, Performance and Environmental Sustainability in the Adoption of Electric Vehicles

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Abstract

Objective: The study investigates how performance, price and environmental sustainability influence customer behaviour towards electric vehicle adoption in Indore, India. **Methods:** The study employed a mixed-method, descriptive and exploratory design. It administered a questionnaire to 438 respondents in the year 2023-24 in Indore. Data analysis was done based on a theoretical framework drawn from the literature, and correlation and MANOVA tests were performed to analyze the correlations between various sustainable factors of EV adoption in four-wheeler and owned vehicle segments. **Findings:** This study on electric vehicles (EVs) has examined correlations relating to age, performance, price, and environmental concerns. Age was found to have a negative correlation with EV price (-0.036), a weak correlation with performance (0.025), and a weak correlation with environment (0.019). Performance strongly correlated with price at 0.560, performance and environment at 0.355, and price and environment at 0.429. The results of MANOVA reported no significant differences in EV adoption case-wise for the age groups of 18-24, 25-34, 35-44 and 45+. Although Wilk's Lambda of 0.991 and partial Eta Squared of 0.003 supported the null hypothesis. Discriminant analysis identified performance and environment instead of price; performance and environment sustainability are the two key factors that have higher significance in EV adoption among the age group 35-44 and 45+. **Novelty:** The study provides a new perspective on EV adoption by challenging age-based marketing strategies. Environmentally conscious consumers are willing to pay a premium price for EVs, considering it a long-term sustainability investment. The study highlights performance and environmental benefits as key drivers of adoption, particularly among aged consumers, contracting traditional assumptions that younger demographics are the primary market for EVs.

Keywords: Indore; E-vehicles; Perception; Adoption; Sustainable Transportation

1 Introduction

Indore’s transition to a metropolitan city has been working to become more sustainable through initiatives like waste management, Urban planning and community engagement. With the demand for four wheelers, a noticeable shift towards EVs is found among the Indore citizens. The shift in trend is backed by the perception of sustainability, reducing recurring costs, and low maintenance costs associated with EVs. However, challenges such as more need for charging infrastructures, product type, affordability, awareness, preferences, higher initial costs, concern for safety, design and limited model in EVs persist. The status of Indore aligns with the factors influencing the adoption of EVs in the city. price is a critical factor influencing EV adoption in Indore, as higher initial cost of EVs is more than the traditional four-wheeler segments. The need for better performing models is required for the longer driving range in metropolitan areas, Indore citizens are drawn towards EVs due to concern for environmental benefits. The city is growing as cleaner and greener transport fosters easy EV adoption. The lack of a robust charging station network hinders wider adoption in the city. Also, Indore’s work on sustainability is shifting among public perceptions.

Hence, the study exploring the effect of price, performance and environmental sustainability in adopting electric vehicles is a progressive landmark to contribute to the goal of a 100% sustainable transport network by 2030. The study exploring the effect of price, performance, and environmental sustainability in adopting electric vehicles has addressed the contribution of recent authors (Table 1) to EV adoption. Many studies, such as Bharadwaj⁽¹⁾, Chakravarty⁽²⁾, and Gong et al.⁽³⁾, have pointed high initial cost of EVs is a major barrier to EV adoption. Duggal⁽⁴⁾, Mahal & Patil⁽⁵⁾, and Khurana et al.⁽⁶⁾ noted the performance limitations, Chakravarty⁽²⁾, Khurana et al.⁽⁶⁾, and Neves et al.⁽⁷⁾ identified a lack of charging infrastructure in various countries as the key issue for EV adoption. Duggal⁽⁴⁾ and Chaturvedi et al.⁽⁸⁾ highlight the lack of segmentation to identify EV adoption. The current study exploring the effect of price, performance, and environmental sustainability in adopting electric vehicles will explore how eco-conscious behaviour (Price, performance, environmental sustainability) are most likely to adopt EVs. The comprehensive understanding of barriers and enablers of EV adoption in Indore helps to overcome challenges faced and will make market strategies, policy measures and consumer education initiatives to increase EV adoption in Indore.

Table 1. Notable contribution of authors to EVs

Study Focus	Key Findings	Research Gap
Examines the future potential of electric vehicles (EVs) in India, highlighting opportunities and challenges in achieving widespread adoption ⁽¹⁾ .	The growth of EVs in India is well positioned, but adoption remains slow due to challenges such as high cost, limited charging infrastructure and technological constraints.	The study lacks an in-depth analysis of region-specific adoption barriers in India. However, it does cover demographics, age, and consumer behaviour towards EVs in different market segments.
The study examines the status and future of EVs in India ⁽²⁾ .	Indian demand lower EV prices compared to other countries. Charging infrastructure is a major problem behind EV adoption. Technology limitations make India dependent on importing EV components, particularly batteries.	It lacks policy measures to improve charging infrastructure and local supply chain development to enhance EV sustainability. It does not examine any demographic factors of age to know EV adoption in India.
Analyze customer preferences for EV and government policies in Australia using a latent class discrete choice model ⁽³⁾ .	The most preferred financial incentive is a rebate on the initial cost of an EV, as EVs are perceived as expensive.	The study fails to examine non-financial factors such as environmental concerns, performance and infrastructure. It also does not examine whether age affects consumer preferences for incentives.
Market segmentation’s role in improving EV adoption in India ⁽⁴⁾ .	The study analyzed the Indian electric car market. Market segmentation is beneficial to identify the acceptance of EVs.	It does not explore whether different age groups perceive EV performance, price and environmental benefits differently.
To study the feasibility of EVs in India ⁽⁵⁾ .	Despite policies, the Indian EV market remains slow, and the transition towards e-vehicle is progressing slowly.	It does not explore how performance, price, and environmental sustainability shape consumer perception in India. It also lacks an analysis of consumer behaviour and the demographic influence of age on EV adoption.

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<p>It examines the factors affecting consumer adoption of EVs in India^{(6), (9), (10)}.</p>	<p>High EV Costs, lack of infrastructure, time constraints and range anxiety hinder adoption. Consumer attitude is a key mediator influencing EV adoption.</p>	<p>The study fails to explore regional variation in India's consumer perceptions, infrastructural challenges, demographic factors, and age.</p>
<p>Analyze the factors influencing the transition to Electric Vehicles (EV) across 24 EU countries from 2010 to 2016⁽⁷⁾.</p>	<p>Technological progress, reflected in increased BEV and PHEV usage, is key to EV adoption. Charging infrastructure is a major driver of electric mobility.</p>	<p>The study does not explore how emerging technologies, such as solid-state batteries and ultra-fast charging, impact EV adoption. The study does not explore demographic and age factors to find trends in the EV Transition.</p>
<p>To study the consumption motives (hedonic, gain and normative) responsible for strengthening consumer's intention towards purchase behaviour for Electric Vehicle (EV)⁽⁸⁾.</p>	<p>Hedonic motives were found to have the strongest influences on purchase intentions.</p>	<p>It lacks mediating effects on various factors age impacting comprehensive understanding of consumer purchase behaviour for EVs.</p>
<p>A comprehensive analysis of factors influencing electric vehicle (EV) adoption, use, and repurchase behaviour⁽¹¹⁾</p>	<p>The study finds regional factors that impact EV adoptions, EV attributes such as driving range, safety, fuel efficiency, charging duration, and cost-related factors that need improvement to enhance consumer appeal. Environmental attitudes also play a crucial role in shaping repurchase behaviour.</p>	<p>The study lacks insights into how functional barriers shape consumer behaviours in EV adoption and use. It also does not find differentiated policies tailored to various consumer segments.</p>
<p>Analyze the perception of Vadodara residents regarding e-vehicles⁽¹²⁾</p>	<p>The residents of Vadodara do not favour EVs; they prefer other vehicles over EVs despite environmental concerns.</p>	<p>It does not examine how different demographics and ages impact EV adoption.</p>
<p>Explore EV owners' perception and satisfaction levels in Mandya^{(13), (14)}</p>	<p>EV businesses face competition from traditional businesses, and customers appreciate low maintenance costs but are dissatisfied with a limited travel range</p>	<p>The study lacks insights into exploring limited consumer behaviour beyond cost; also, no differentiated policies for different regions to develop EV infrastructure or EV adoption were found</p>
<p>Analyze EV data focusing on energy consumption⁽¹⁵⁾.</p>	<p>No correlation was found between charging speed and energy consumption, positive correlation between energy consumption and range 7 max velocity, negative correlation between energy consumption and correlation.</p>	<p>The study fails to compare performance, price and environmental sustainability with real-world driving conditions.</p>
<p>Analyze the scientific contribution of EVs from 1955 to 2021⁽¹⁵⁾</p>	<p>The study explores 104,344 authors from 149 countries with 225,445 collaborative links to identify the most relevant publications in diverse research areas in EV development</p>	<p>The study lacks insight impact of technological advancements, environment sustainability, price, and performance to know EV research trends</p>
<p>Investigate how traffic circumstances affect an electric vehicle's energy consumption⁽¹⁶⁾.</p>	<p>It was found that traffic conditions significantly impact EV energy consumption. Frequent stops and slow driving lead to high energy usage.</p>	<p>It lacks insights into how demographic variables, such as age and driving habits, influence EV adoption.</p>
<p>To explore the factors influencing the decision to buy electric vehicles in Switzerland⁽¹⁷⁾.</p>	<p>Individuals in Switzerland prioritize the economic Aspects, such as ownership costs and the performance and features of electric cars when considering a switch from conventional vehicles.</p>	<p>It does not explore demographic factors such as age influence intention to buy an electric car between regions and areas with other cultures.</p>
<p>Analyze operations managers' perception of electric vehicle (EV) adoption in business processes⁽¹⁸⁾.</p>	<p>EV adoption in businesses benefits operation managers by allowing them to work in an eco-friendly business model, reduces costs and tax benefits, and contributes to sustainability.</p>	<p>The study lacks industry-specific challenges when considering price, performance and environmental concerns in EV adoption in business.</p>
<p>Assess the current state of EVs in Eastern Europe, examine customer awareness towards EVs, and examine environmental aspects such as decarbonization and emission reduction⁽¹⁹⁾.</p>	<p>EV adoption is growing slowly in Eastern Europe, and customer awareness is limited. Battery development is crucial in reducing Greenhouse gas emissions, and decarbonization of power generation is essential for EV integration.</p>	<p>The study does not explore demographic factors, age, regional differences in consumer adoption behaviour, or economic incentives for EV Ownership.</p>

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Assess the current state of sustainable transport in Georgia. Also, examine policy commitments and future advancements towards integrating electric mobility in public transport ⁽²⁰⁾ . Examine the expansion of the electric vehicle (EV) market in Europe ⁽²¹⁾ .	Georgia has committed to reduce total emissions by 35% under the Paris Agreement, with a 15% target to reduce transport emissions. Important steps have been taken in Tbilisi and Batumi to integrate electric mobility. EV technology is advancing rapidly, with improvements in battery efficiency, charging infrastructure and vehicle performance	It does not explore demographic or economic feasibility regarding the sustainability of electrifying public transport. The study lacks a country-specific analysis of adoption rate and policy effectiveness. It also does not explore how demographic factors such as income and age influence EV adoption.
Develop six strategies to establish framework conditions in energy markets for integrating smart EV charging as a European standard ⁽²²⁾ .	The smart EV charging services market is expanding, but consumer awareness of cost savings and environmental benefits such as renewable energy integration remains low.	It lacks a detailed assessment of policy and regulatory challenges in implementing smart charging across European countries. Further, it lacks insights to explore the demographic and age adoption of Smart EV charging.

Hasan examined customers' choices regarding buying electric vehicles⁽⁹⁾. Duggal investigated the factors affecting market segmentation and product acceptance of EVs globally⁽⁴⁾. Several scholars have examined various important issues, such as the feasibility of EVs⁽⁵⁾, enhanced public awareness and prediction about vehicle preferences, and several aspects of the adoption of EVs, such as costs, charging facilities, awareness of EVs, availability of different models, safety risks involved in EVs, instrumental and symbolic attributes, and incentives⁽¹¹⁾. Challenges for the electric vehicle business in Mandya explore owners' perceptions of the electric vehicle business. On the other hand, the study focuses on owners' perceptions and satisfaction decisions about electric vehicles⁽¹²⁾.

The study was conducted to ascertain why the Indore people adopted EVs. It included three factors: the effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental factors. This research would be helpful for future studies related to the adoption of EVs, manufacturers of EVs, and policymakers.

Problem Statement:

Many factors influence the adoption of electric vehicles (EVs), like product type, affordability, awareness, preferences, cost, charging structure, availability of models, concern for safety, and design. Having become a metropolitan city, Indore has increased its demand for four-wheelers. People are moving toward electric vehicles more because it gives them the feeling of sustainability, reduced recurring costs and low maintenance. Hence, this trend directed a study regarding obtaining views of the four-wheeler owners, particularly like effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental factors, to develop a strategy to enhance wider acceptance of EVs in Indore City.

Theoretical Framework and Literature Review:

Numerous global studies have explored the driving forces and challenges behind adopting electric vehicles (EVs). These investigations have examined various factors, including EV cost, driving range per charge, battery recharge time, and the availability of both financial and non-financial incentives. Reviewing existing literature has provided insights into global and regional trends in e-vehicle adoption, sustainable practices, and customer attitudes. A literature review (Table 1) has identified several attributes suitable for this study and their respective variables.

Performance of EV:

Authors have explored several aspects that influenced car owners' adoption of an EV in India. They concluded that attitudes influenced the adoption of electric vehicles⁽⁶⁾,⁽¹³⁾,⁽¹⁴⁾. Similarly, Parmar and Pradhan predicted future vehicle preferences, environmental considerations, and public perception of the global automobile industry on electrical vehicle dependability of males and females⁽¹¹⁾. Owners' perceptions of the electric car industry reveal that customers are more satisfied with the reduced maintenance costs than the inconvenience of long-distance trips⁽¹²⁾.

Skuzza *et al*⁽¹⁷⁾ ascertained how traffic circumstances affect an electric vehicle's energy consumption and demonstrated that frequent stops and slow driving increase energy consumption⁽¹⁴⁾. Madziel and Campisi presented a methodology to analyze electric vehicle data, particularly emphasizing the energy consumption parameter⁽¹⁵⁾. Novas *et al*. highlighted the wide variety of areas involved in EV development and broadened knowledge about EVs and efficiency⁽¹⁶⁾. The cost of ownership, performance and features, and social influence variables inform marketing and communication strategies to promote electric car adoption in Switzerland⁽¹⁸⁾. The diverse consumption motives, including hedonic, gain, and normative factors, reinforce consumers'

intentions towards Electric Vehicle (EV) purchase behaviour investigated. The quality characteristics structure of battery electric vehicles (BEVs) has a significant force due to their low emissions and high energy efficiency⁽²³⁾.

Price of EV:

Duggal described the Indian electric car market, highlighting the benefits of market segmentation in identifying target markets and increasing product acceptance⁽⁴⁾. Mahal and Patil examined the feasibility of electric vehicles in India, focusing on the country's small EV market despite enacting policies, as fossil resource depletion and rising costs demand alternative energy sources⁽⁵⁾. Incorporating EVs into business processes offers various benefits to organizations, such as lowered operational costs, environment-conscious eco-friendly operations, tax benefits, reduced dependence on fossil fuels, lower emissions, and fostering sustainable development⁽¹⁹⁾,⁽²⁴⁾. Gong et al.⁽³⁾ analyzed incentives for buying and using electric vehicles (EVs) and found upfront cost rebates for the EV market. The effects of high-capability batteries and EV discounts on the EV in Los Angeles, California, conclude that EVs' Price presents a greater adoption barrier than the EV range⁽²⁵⁾.

Environment Concerns of EV:

Horváth *et al.* emphasized the role of EV adoption in achieving climate protection goals and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Recognizing the impact of personalized transport⁽²⁰⁾, the Government of Georgia seeks sustainable mobility options, including hybrid and electric vehicles⁽²¹⁾. An insight was provided into EV technologies, characteristics, advantages, disadvantages, opportunities, and barriers in Europe, considering the mass-market appeal of EVs⁽²²⁾. Authors outlined strategies for smart charging, highlighting the lack of consumer information on its savings and environmental benefits⁽²⁶⁾. Neves et al. analyzed factors supporting the transition to Electric Vehicles, including policy, social, economic, environmental, and technical aspects⁽⁷⁾. Car buyers' preferences and motivations are heterogeneous, suggesting "Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEVs)" as the most promising PEV option for broad market appeal⁽²⁷⁾.

Summary of Literature Review and Research Gap:

Through an exhaustive literature review, two types of research gaps were identified, i.e., evidence gap and theoretical gap. The literature review expresses several attributes studied countries like India, Austria, Indonesia, Germany, Switzerland, Australia, Belgium, Poland, Central Europe, China, Japan, Canada, and Norway and different states of the countries such as Bangkok, California, Los Angeles, Tumkur City and Flanders. The electronic vehicle started in 2019 at Indore; no study has been done on the attributes and variables (performance of EVs, Price of EVs, and environmental concern of EVs) identified for the study. Thus, this study will investigate Sustainable factors influencing e-vehicle adoption in Indore and related factors to fill the evidence gap. Similarly, there is a theoretical gap in understanding how adopting e-vehicles might impact urban mobility patterns, especially among different age groups of society, and transportation behaviour in Indore.

Research Question:

The Research questions on the influence of sustainable factors and customer perception on e-vehicle adoption in Indore are:

- What are the sustainable factors that influence customers to adopt EVs?
- What sustainable choices do customers perceive while buying EVs?
- How do the combined effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental factors across different age groups Influence the adoption of e-vehicles in Indore?

2 Methodology

James underscored pragmatism, a philosophy that evaluates ideas based on experimentation and practical outcomes. It asserts that truth is changeable, human actions shape academic inquiry, truth is not absolute, meaning and action are linked, and ideas are judged by their ability to ensure consistency and predictability⁽²⁸⁾. The study is descriptive and uses a pragmatic paradigm⁽²⁸⁾. It embraces the positivist philosophical alignment, which states that quantitative and deductive reasoning are employed in the research, moving from general to specific. Through empirical and systematic investigation, the combined approach analyses and measures the influence of sustainable factors and customer perception on e-vehicle adoption in Indore and generalizes the insights drawn from the study.

The dataset of the study is available at <https://osf.io/adfm3>.

The difference between the proposed method and the existing method:

This research examines the combined effects of Performance, Price, and Environment on all-age adoption of electric vehicles within Indore, first assuming an equal elevation of importance for all factors. However, it discovers two major factors- Performance and Environmental attitudes towards EVs. Most importantly, it shows that age groups, specifically 35-44 and 45+, strongly and reliably associate these factors with their preference regarding choosing four-wheeled EVs. These findings suggest that performance capability and environmental sense provide a better strategy for middle-aged and older to increase the adoption of these innovations.

Research Design:

A mixed-method approach, employing both descriptive and exploratory research designs, was utilized through a survey to investigate the influence of sustainable factors and customer perceptions regarding e-vehicle adoption in Indore. The questionnaire was meticulously crafted to address the research objectives, encompassing inquiries regarding charging station availability, government incentives, and customer awareness regarding e-vehicle benefits. During the 2023-24 period, the study employed convenience-based sampling to gather responses from Indore residents spanning various demographics. The questionnaire, facilitated through Google Forms, was distributed via WhatsApp, Facebook, and email. Data Analysis was undertaken through descriptive and inferential statistics tests. Correlation and MANOVA analysis were used to examine patterns in sustainable choices and customer perceptions regarding e-vehicle adoption among different age cohorts to identify multivariate relationships in the data.

Validity and Reliability Test:

The validity was tested through bivariate correlations on all the items. It was found insignificant for occupation and satisfaction with the current EV Price, and the other variables were found valid in the questionnaire. So, the critical value for Pearson’ r’ was 0.095, measured at 0.05 significance level on Degree of Freedom (438-2). The combined reliability score of 30 items exhibits satisfactory reliability, as Cronbach’s alpha score is above 0.6.

Normality Test:

The normality of the data was assessed through Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests in SPSS—the significant value of p (<0.05) for all factors. The sample data set’s distribution is skewed; a non-parametric test was used.

3 Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile:

IBM SPSS 20 was used to analyze the sample’s socio-demographic features to replicate most of the population’s characteristics and examine research issues. Table 2 shows descriptive statistics of the respondents. Male customers adopt e-vehicles more than female customers. Customers aged 25-34 occupied the highest proportion of the sample, followed by customers aged 45 and above, 35-44 years and 18-24 years.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics	Frequency	%	Descriptive Statistics	Frequency	%
Gender			Monthly Income		
Male	240	54.8	Below 1 Lakh	82	18.7
Female	198	45.2	1-3 Lakhs	156	35.6
Total	438	100.0	3-5 Lakhs	106	24.2
Age			Above 5 Lakhs	94	21.5
18-24	63	14.4	Total	438	100.0
25-34	148	33.8	Preference of EVs Company		
35-44	112	25.6	Hyundai	84	19.2
45 and above	115	26.3	Kia	51	11.6
Total	438	100.0	Mahindra	33	7.5
Occupation			MG	111	25.3
Self Employed	143	32.6	Tata	159	36.3
Salaried Employee	124	28.3	Total	438	100.0
Unemployed/Retired	128	29.2	Availability of Charging Stations		
Student	43	9.8	Strongly Agree	95	21.7
Total	438	100.0	Agree	143	32.6
			Neutral	124	28.3
			Disagree	64	14.6
			Strongly Disagree	12	2.7
			Total	438	100.0

Self-employed comprised the largest segment of the sample, followed by unemployed/retired individuals, salaried employees and students constitute the smallest proportion. Most customers had a monthly income of 1-3 lakhs, followed by those with

incomes of 3-5 lakhs, above 5 lakhs and below 1 lakh. Analysis of customers’ preferences regarding electric vehicle companies in Indore revealed Tata as the most preferred, followed by MG, Hyundai, Kia, and Mahindra, decreasing orders in four-wheeler EV segments. 32.6% of customers agreed, 28.3% were neutral, 21.7% strongly agreed, 14.6% disagreed, and 2.7% strongly disagreed with the availability of charging stations representing the minority viewpoint.

Hypothesis Testing:

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant difference when considering the combined effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental factors on adopting e-vehicles across age groups.

Inferential Statistics:

As users might adopt e-vehicles based on different arguments, the study examined Performance, Price, and environmental-related variables when using electric vehicles. The study examined the independent variable -Age Cohorts (18-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45 and above)- and the dependent variable—performance, Price, and environmental concerns of EVs (Table 3). A correlation analysis examined the relationship between age, performance, price, and environmental concerns of electric vehicles (EVs). The results revealed negative correlations between age and price of EV (-.036), strong positive correlation between Performance and Price of EV (0.560), Performance and Environment of EV (0.355), Price and Environment of EV (0.429) as well as moderate correlation between age and performance of EV (0.025), age and environment of EV (0.019). Additionally, MANOVA analysis was employed to assess significant differences in e-vehicle adoption across age groups, considering the combined effects of performance, price, and environmental factors.

Table 3. Correlations

		Age	Performance of EV	Price of EV	Environment of EV
Age	Pearson Correlation	1	.025	-.036	.019
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.603	.458	.687
	N	438	438	438	438
Performance of EV	Pearson Correlation	.025	1	.560**	.355**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.603		.000	.000
	N	438	438	438	438
Price of EV	Pearson Correlation	-.036	.560**	1	.429**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.458	.000		.000
	N	438	438	438	438
Environment of EV	Pearson Correlation	.019	.355**	.429**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.687	.000	.000	
	N	438	438	438	438

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The multivariate test statistics for the group variable are provided below, with Partial Eta squared indicating the effect size (Table 4).

Table 4. Multivariate Tests

Effect	Value	F	Hypothesis df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared	
Intercept	Pillai’s Trace	.987	10784.248b	3.000	432.000	.000	.987
	Wilks’ Lambda	.013	10784.248b	3.000	432.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling’s Trace	74.891	10784.248b	3.000	432.000	.000	.987
	Roy’s Largest Root	74.891	10784.248b	3.000	432.000	.000	.987
Age	Pillai’s Trace	.009	.458	9.000	1302.000	.903	.003
	Wilks’ Lambda	.991	.457	9.000	1051.525	.903	.003
	Hotelling’s Trace	.010	.456	9.000	1292.000	.904	.003
	Roy’s Largest Root	.007	.946c	3.000	434.000	.418	.006

a. Design: Intercept + Age

b. Exact statistic

c. The statistic is an upper bound on F that yields a lower bound on the significance level.

Wilk's Lambda determined the statistical significance of the overall multivariate effect, with all multivariate statistics above 0.05. Wilks' Lambda was 0.991, $F(9, 1051.525) = 0.457$, $p < 0.005$, with a Partial Eta Squared of 0.003. Accepting the null hypothesis suggests no significant effect across age groups (18-24, 25-34, 35-44, and 45+) when considering the combined effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental factors in adopting e-vehicles in Indore.

Tests of between-subjects effects were utilized to assess whether there are significant variations in the means of the dependent variables (Performance, Price, and Environmental factors) across different ages (Table 5).

Table 5. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	Performance of EV	.487a	3	.162	.528	.663	.004
	Price of EV	.403b	3	.134	.466	.706	.003
	Environment of EV	.204c	3	.068	.170	.916	.001
Intercept	Performance of EV	6508.119	1	6508.119	21180.066	.000	.980
	Price of EV	6557.079	1	6557.079	22741.522	.000	.981
	Environment of EV	7140.858	1	7140.858	17849.646	.000	.976
Age	Performance of EV	.487	3	.162	.528	.663	.004
	Price of EV	.403	3	.134	.466	.706	.003
	Environment of EV	.204	3	.068	.170	.916	.001
Error	Performance of EV	133.358	434	.307			
	Price of EV	125.136	434	.288			
	Environment of EV	173.624	434	.400			
Total	Performance of EV	7323.000	438				
	Price of EV	7332.938	438				
	Environment of EV	8047.000	438				
Corrected Total	Performance of EV	133.844	437				
	Price of EV	125.539	437				
	Environment of EV	173.829	437				

a. R Squared = .004 (Adjusted R Squared = -.003)
b. R Squared = .003 (Adjusted R Squared = -.004)
c. R Squared = .001 (Adjusted R Squared = -.006)

In this analysis, the significance value for EV performance, price, and environment exceeds 0.05. The partial ETA squared is less than 0.19. So, it appears there is no interaction effect. Consequently, the model is deemed not statistically significant. The Wilk's Lamda test for DFA result reveals functions 1 through 3 have $p = .903$, functions 2 through 3 have $p = 0.863$ and function 3 have $p = 0.755$.

Table 6. Wilks' Lambda

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1 through 3	.991	4.118	9	.903
2 through 3	.997	1.291	4	.863
3	1.000	.098	1	.755

Table 6 reveals that the functions have a lesser capacity for discrimination. The standardized canonical discriminant function coefficients and Table 7 demonstrate the importance of independent variables in predicting the dependent variable, facilitating comparisons across variables measured on various scales.

In Figure 1 (Canonical Discriminant Functions Plot), the dispersion of age groups to Performance and Environmental factors in the adoption of EVs is depicted. The combined group plot effectively demonstrated the relationships between the variables and the groups. Variable 1 has positive values on the initial variations for 35-44 years and 45 years and above. Overall, the age groups 35-44 years and 45 years and above have relatively good and canonical significance with Performance and Environment factors in EV adoption. Hence, Performance and Environment factors in EV adoption affect different age groups (Figure 1).

Table 7. Standardized Canonical Discriminant Function Coefficients

	Function		
	1	2	3
Performance of EV	.980	.476	-.554
Price of EV	-1.084	.653	-.002
Environment of EV	.385	-.003	1.052

Age	Function		
	1	2	3
18-24	-.183	.003	.013
25-34	-.008	-.015	-.020
35-44	.050	.081	.005
45 and above	.062	-.061	.014

Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means

Fig 1. Canonical Discriminant Functions

4 Discussion

Male customers in Indore are more likely to embrace e-vehicles due to variables including gender-specific mobility patterns and accessibility limitations, which influence their unique preferences and choices for sustainable transportation. The young age groups 25-34 years in Indore are more likely to prefer e-vehicles than other age groups, and they show a higher likelihood of adopting newer technology, a tech-savvy attitude, potential alignment with environmental ideals, and a stronger understanding and acceptance of sustainable practices and environmentally friendly modes of transportation. Self-employed comprised the largest segment in occupation, showing high interest in e-vehicle adoption compared to other occupations. A stronger concern for environmental sustainability, Customers with 1-3 lakhs monthly income are eager to buy EVs compared to other monthly income groups. Due to its brand reputation, affordable pricing, and potentially favourable features, Tata holds a higher representation of electric vehicle preferences in Indore among four-wheeler segments than other EV segments. 32.6% of customers agree with the availability of sufficient charging stations in Indore. The availability of charging stations has changed individuals' perceptions and created their inclination towards EVs. EVs' environmental factors, i.e., reducing emissions and ecological benefits, are consistent motivators for purchasing e-vehicles. High pickup, good mileage, and long battery life vary among age groups because different age demographics prioritize these performance aspects differently based on their needs and preferences.

According to the investigation, the correlation analysis suggests age appears to have a negative correlation between age and the Price of EV (-.036). At the same time, there is a strong positive correlation between the performance and Price of EV (0.560), the Performance and Environment of EV (0.355), price and environment of EV (0.429). This means price and performance perceptions are closely linked with each other, also, individuals perceive EVs with high performance as more likely to contribute positively to environmental goals. Environmentally conscious consumers are likely to accept higher prices for EVs and view it as an investment contributing to sustainability.

Multivariate test statistics (MANOVA) Wilks' Lambda, Pillai's Trace, Lawley-Hotelling Trace, and Roy's Largest Root indicated no significant effect across age groups (18-24, 25-34, 35-44, and 45+) on the combined effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental concerns in e-vehicles adoption in Indore. These factors have a consistent impact on e-vehicle adoption across age groups. Tests of subjects were utilized to assess no interaction effect (Performance, Price, and Environmental factors) across different ages. The null hypothesis was rejected, which indicates all factors are positively affecting the adoption of EVs in Indore. This result can be generalized in common. The variances of all three factors, performance, price and environment, are not found to be uniform, thus indicating that it is not uniform in all age groups undertaken in this study. This suggests a generalized strategy, rather than age-specific targeting, may be effective for promoting e-vehicles, as the impact of these factors remains consistent across age demographics. Customized solutions are required for each age group separately.

The discriminant function analysis indicates limited differentiation by age group, with Performance and Environment factors being the main drivers of variation in attitudes toward EVs. The negative weight of price suggests it has less influence, making performance and environmental benefits more impactful across age demographics. The combined group plot shows that the 35-44 and 45+ age groups have strong, significant associations with Performance and Environment factors in EV adoption. This suggests that targeting these factors—particularly performance and environmental benefits—could effectively engage older age groups in EV adoption.

User satisfaction with the Price of current EVs may be influenced by factors such as affordability, incentives, and perceived value compared to traditional vehicles. The high awareness about subsidies provided by the Indian government on EVs within the sample could be attributed to effective government communication, media coverage, and the significant impact of financial incentives on consumer decision-making regarding EV adoption.

Past studies have explored various factors influencing EV Adoption, such as environmental concerns, technology, infrastructure, rebates, discounts and social readiness. Some studies also highlighted the appeal of EV adoption in different countries due to the efficiency of high-capacity batteries, low emission and financial incentives given at the government or organizational level. Past research often compares across various demographics without focusing on age-related attitudes and tailored marketing strategies for specific age groups adopting EVs. The current study focuses on age-related attitudes towards performance, price and environmental factors in EV adoption in Indore. The novelty of the current research is that age does not significantly change the attitude of buyers towards these variables. Instead, the study focused on the generalized approach to EV adoption, which may be more effective than age-specific strategies. Consumers aged 35-44 and 45+ were found to have a strong association with performance and environmental factors, which could inform policymakers and marketers to aim for old age groups, which contradicts traditional assumptions that the EV market is for young consumers.

5 Conclusion

This study sheds light on the understanding of the Indian population, especially Indore City, in adopting e-vehicles. Male students aged between 25-34 show a high preference for EVs. Tata is the most preferred EV brand in the four-wheeler segment, and Indore has a scope of charging stations. Descriptive statistical analysis, Correlation and MANOVA Analysis were used to know the significant difference in adopting e-vehicles across different age groups when considering the combined effects of Performance, Price, and Environmental factors. The findings collectively reveal that age is not a significant differentiator in attitudes toward Performance, Price, and Environmental factors for e-vehicle adoption in Indore, as supported by the multivariate tests; it suggests that a generalized approach may be sufficient for promoting e-vehicles rather than an age-specific strategy. Customized messaging could enhance engagement by tailoring emphasis on specific factors—especially performance and environmental benefits—for older demographics. The generational divide plays an important role in assessing perceptions or evaluations of electric vehicles regarding performance, price and environmental concerns. The study can help frame new policies and practices for sustainable transportation solutions in smart cities. This suggests that marketing and policy strategies should focus on emphasizing the core benefits of e-vehicles—such as performance and environmental impact—across all age groups.

This research contributes significantly to academic understanding and practical implementation for the sustainable development of Electric Vehicles (EVs). We anticipate that future research will delve deeper into fostering improved customer satisfaction, particularly concerning price, performance, and environmental values in the context of EVs.

5.1 Implications and Future Scope of the Study

Theoretical Implications :

The study on the influence of sustainable factors and customer perception on e-vehicle adoption exerts several theoretical implications that help to refine existing theories and develop new models to predict e-vehicle adoption behaviour. Theoretical implications in the field of research generate new policy decisions and industry practices, enabling governments and industries to adopt sustainable transportation options, such as e-bus transportation systems. The lack of significant variation across age groups in attitudes toward Performance, Price, and Environmental factors challenges existing theories prioritizing age as a key variable in understanding adoption behaviour. There is a need for theoretical models that integrate factors beyond demographics to capture the complexities of consumer decision-making in sustainable transportation.

Managerial Implications:

Promoting Performance and Environmental factors enhances customer engagement and drives adoption rates across all age groups. Market research should focus on factors beyond demographics and identify shared values that drive EV adoption, highlighting environmental sustainability. Product developers and designers of e-vehicles may research innovative benefits and attributes that meet customer expectations regarding performance, price, and environmental sustainability. Government and B2B Industries may design an effective incentive plan and policy to encourage customers to choose sustainable transportation. Manufacturers, energy companies and technology providers can analyze existing and past trends and may use collaborative strategies to identify opportunities in e-vehicle markets.

Limitations of the Study and Future Scope of Research:

The sample size is 434, but with an increased sample, a study could give a more realistic view as the study is conducted at Indore. This study may encounter limitations due to self-reported data, potential sampling bias, and the cross-sectional design, which limits the ability to draw causal inferences. Indore was chosen as the area of study based on infrastructural development, cleanliness, etc.; other cities cannot be considered due to time and scope limitations. The study was exclusively conducted on adopting a four-wheeler of owned EVs. Two-wheeler EVs and rental vehicles were not considered, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other segments of the EV market.

The influence of sustainable factors and customer perception on e-vehicle adoption is limited to demographic factors such as occupation and satisfaction with the current Price of EVs, which did not account for the regional variation within the city, i.e., rural, urban, and semi-urban areas.

Future scope:

The study also offers a guide for future research in areas such as:- Exploring the adoption of two-wheeler EVs and rental EVs to provide a comprehensive understanding of the EV market. Assessing the collaboration and partnership perspective between manufacturing, Energy companies and technology providers to raise more opportunities in E-Vehicles; Analysing adoption patterns and buying behaviour among e-vehicle users of Smart Cities; Investigating the social and cultural factors associated with e-vehicle adoption in different emerging markets in Asia; Urban Planning and Sustainable Transportation Practices in Smart Cities of India; low-speed EVs, the under-18 consumer segment, and the role that social and cultural dynamics play in

their consumer adoption in the electric vehicle marketplace; and Assessing the technological advancement in e-vehicle strategies regarding Performance, Price, and Environment Sustainability in India.

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